
Geographical Analysis of the Changing Scenario of Municipal Council Election in Gonda District

Akhand Pratap Pal*

Guest Faculty, Geography Department PRSU Naini, Prayagraj, UP.

Ashish Kumar Mishra

Research Scholar, Geography Department, PG college Patti, Pratapgarh UP mishraak.0138@gmail.com

Shikha Yadav

Department of Geography, Miranda House, University of Delhi, New Delhi 110007 (India);
shikhayadav356@gmail.com

*Corresponding Email: akhand30@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

In this research paper analyses the election pattern of Municipal council elections in Gonda district. The research will conduct three different Municipal councils (Gonda, Nawabganj and Karnailganj) in years of 2012, 2017 and 2023. This paper explores the changing strategies of election candidate behaviour in different groups. The paper discusses the negative and positive behaviour during a part of election years. In sub-category like Party members and independent member (regional party) growing influence of regional parties in Indian democracy. Electoral geography is recent in Political geography, its express political phenomena in different aspects of research. This research based on both primary & secondary data to expresses the spatial pattern in elections, how behaviour of candidates and voters change in local elections and into the general elections.

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Introduction- In history, earlier election starts from ancient Athens (Rome) and modern elections conducted in the norms of Europe and North America in 17th century for a representative government.

An election is a process for selecting a public representative those work for citizen welfare, nation building also fulfil the objective of peoples and conduct dialogues between nation as representative. During election peoples have voting rights to voted party or individual to complete his future aims for certain time period. Election is basic natures in humans like, ancient period and tribal communities lead by Mukhiya or Sardar (Prime authorities). Election is one of the major events for developed social values in human and election show the human behaviour and status of the society. Indian democracy is inextricable democracy in world, voting behaviours are many times impacted by (law, political science, history, statistics, public opinion, sociology, marketing, social psychology, economics and culture as following disciplinaries) therefore, Election geography is sub-discipline under Political geography which express, the how geography and social sciences impact and construct a nation blue-print. In Indian election system is construct by constitutionals ways, which has been conducted into central and state level elections. In parliamentary system of governance are bicameral legislature in central level, Lok Sabha (House of the people) and Rajya Sabha (Council of States) are main body, on the other hand unicameral in state level Vidhan Sabha (State Legislative Assembly) and Vidhan Parishad (State Legislative Council). Local level elections are in conducted in Municipal elections (Urban local bodies) and Panchayat elections (Rural local bodies). All the elections are proceeded in two manners Direct Election: (Lok Sabha, State Legislative Assembly, Municipal elections, Panchayat elections) and Indirect election: (Rajya Sabha, Presidential election, State Legislative Council and nominative members). So, this is way hug geographical identity of India, makes festival of election in different space and time.

Objective

- 1-To present a geographical analysis of the Municipal Council elections of Gonda district.
- 2-To present a temporal analysis of the changes taking place at the Municipal Council level in the number of Municipal Council Chairman and Members.
- 3-To present suggestions regarding the changes taking place in the number of reserved seats in the Municipal Council elections.

Data Source & Methodology-

Both primary and secondary data have been used in the presented research. Secondary data was collected from the data published by the Election Commission of Uttar Pradesh. In this research, a geographical analysis of the members and presidents who won under male, female, Scheduled Caste,

Other Backward Class, party member and independent member was done under the general municipal council elections of the year 2012, year 2017 and year 2023. Along with this, the analysis of male, female, Scheduled Caste, Other Backward Class, party member and independent member has been done in the temporal perspective under the general municipal council elections of the year 2012, year 2017 and year 2023. Tables and charts have been used as per the need for easy study of this research.

Research Area:-District Gonda is located in the state of Uttar Pradesh of India. Its longitudinal extension is 81°31' East to 82°86' East and latitudinal extension is 26°47' North to 27°20' North. Gonda district borders the following districts of Uttar Pradesh. It is bordered by Shravasti and Balrampur districts in the north, Basti district in the east, Ayodhya district in the south, Bahraich district in the north-west and Barabanki district in the south-west. The total area of Gonda district is 4003 square kilometers. The soil of Gonda district is of sandy, loamy and sandy-loamy type. All three types of crops, Kharif, Rabi and Zaid, are grown in Gonda district. According to Census 2011, the total population of Gonda district is 3433919 in which 1787146 is male population and 1646773 is female population. 541247 families reside in Gonda district. The average sex ratio of the district is 921. According to the 2011 census, 6.6 percent of the population lives in urban areas and 93.4 percent of the population lives in rural areas. The average population density of Gonda district is 858. Saryu, Visuhi, Manwar, Tedhi, Kuano are the main rivers here. The soil of Gonda district is of sandy, loamy and sandy-loamy type. All three types of crops, Kharif, Rabi and Zaid, are grown in Gonda district. According to Census 2011, the total population of Gonda district is 3433919 in which 1787146 is male population and 1646773 is female population. In district Gonda, located in Uttar Pradesh, consists of four tehsils: (Colonelganj, Gonda, Mankapur, and Tarabganj). It is spread into three municipal councils and 16 blocks, with a total of 1,817 villages spread across the district. This administrative structure serves the diverse needs of the local population, with each tehsil playing a key role in governance and rural development.

Analysis-In the year 1992, the urban governance system was established by the 74th Constitutional Amendment. Under which Nagar Palika Parishad (municipal council) was established. Nagar Palika Parishad (municipal council) is one of the 8 types of urban local governance in India. The 74th Constitutional Amendment of 1992 added a new Part 9A to the Constitution of India. It was named Nagar Palika and provisions of Articles 243T to 243YG were included. Due to this Act, a new 12th Schedule was also added to the Constitution. This list mentions 18 executive subjects of municipalities. The 74th Constitutional Amendment Act provides for the structure of three types of municipalities

(Nagar Panchayat, Nagar Palika Parishad and Nagar Palika Nigam) in every state, in which Municipal Council is formed for small urban areas. In Uttar Pradesh, the members and chairman of the Municipal Council are directly elected by the voters of the Municipal Council. Their tenure is generally 5 years. This Act provides reservation for Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes in every Municipality in proportion to their population and the population of the total Municipal Area. Besides this, it provides reservation for women on one third of the total seats. The State Legislature lays down the law for reservation of the post of Chairman in Municipality for Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes and women. The analysis of the general elections of Gonda Municipal Council, Nawabganj Municipal Council and Karnailganj Municipal Council of Gonda district in the year 2012, year 2017 and year 2023 is as follows-

Table-1. District-Gonda, Municipal Council Data (Chairman & Member) Year-2012

Sr. No.	Municipal council	Male	Female	SC	OBC	General	Party Mem.	Ind. Mem.
1	Gonda	17	11	02	13	13	4	24
2	Nawabganj	13	13	02	08	16	0	26
3	Karnailganj	15	11	01	21	04	0	26
	Total	45	35	05	42	33	04	77

Source- Election commission of Uttar Pradesh, Urban General Election Result 2012

According to the table 1.0 & Chart Number 1.0, Urban General election (Municipal council data-2012) result in Gonda district of all municipal council member and chairman. In this election 27 wards in Gonda were 17 winning candidates (including chairmen) in men and 11 candidates in female are winning. In this election in different category like UR-17, OBC-13 and 2 candidates from SC communities. There are 25 victorious in independent members and 04 are associated with political parties. Same as 25 wards in Nawabganj were 13 winning candidates in men and 13 candidates (including chairmen) in female are winning. In this election in different category like (UR-16, OBC-08 and SC-2) communities. There are 26 victorious in independent member. In Karnailganj region there are

Chart -1 District-Gonda, Municipal Council Data (Chairman & Member) Year-2012

Source- Election commission of Uttar Pradesh, Urban General Election Result 2012

25 wards were 15 winning candidates (including chairmen) in men and 11 candidates in female are winning. In this election in different category like UR-04, OBC-21 and 1 candidate from SC communities. There are 26 victorious in independent members and no one can associate with political parties. In previous data winning males are 45 both and females 35 both, category wise UR-33, OBC-42 and SC-5. Total independent members are 77 and party associated winners are only 04.

Table -2 District-Gonda, Municipal Council Data (Chairman & Member) Year-2017

Sr. No.	Municipal council	Male	Female	SC	OBC	General	Party Mem.	Ind. Mem.
1	Gonda	15	13	02	11	15	11	17
2	Nawabganj	17	09	02	10	14	05	21
3	Karnailganj	16	10	01	21	04	02	24
	Total	48	32	05	42	33	18	62

Source- Election commission of Uttar Pradesh, Urban General Election Result 2017

Chart -2 District-Gonda, Municipal Council Data (Chairman & Member) Year-2017

Source- Election commission of Uttar Pradesh, Urban General Election Result 2017

According to the table number 2.0 & Chart Number 2.0, Urban General election (Municipal council data-2017) result in Gonda district of all municipal council member and chairman. In this election 27 wards in Gonda were 15 winning candidates in men and 13 candidates (including chairmen) in female are winning. In this election in different category result like UR-15, OBC-11 and 2 candidates are in SC communities. There are 17 victorious in independent members and 11 are associated with political parties. Same as 25 wards in Nawabganj were 17 winning candidates (including chairmen) in men and 09 candidates in female are winning. In this election in different category like UR-14, OBC10 and 2 candidates in SC communities. There are 21 victorious in independent member and 05 are in different political parties. In Karnailganj there are 25 wards were 16 winning candidates in men and 10 candidates (including chairmen) in female are winning. In this election in different category like UR04, OBC-21 and 1 candidate in SC communities. There are 24 victorious in independent members and 02 are associate with political parties. In previous data winning males are 48 both and females 32, category wise UR-33, OBC-42 and SC-5. Total independent members are 62 and party associated winners are 18 in different parties.

Table-3 District-Gonda, Municipal Council Data (Chairman & Member) Year-2023

Sr. No.	Municipal council	Male	Female	SC	OBC	General	Party Mem.	Ind. Mem.
1	Gonda	17	11	02	14	12	08	20
2	Nawabganj	11	12	02	11	13	04	22
3	Karnailganj	16	10	02	21	03	07	19
	Total	44	33	06	46	37	19	61

Source- Election commission of Uttar Pradesh, Urban General Election Result 2023

Chart -3. District-Gonda Municipal Council Data (Chairman & Member) Year-2023

Source-Source- Election commission of Uttar Pradesh, Urban General Election Result 2023

According to the table number 3.0 & Chart Number 3.0 Urban General election (Municipal council data-2023) result in Gonda district of all municipal council member and chairman. In this election 27 wards in Gonda were 17 winning candidates in men and 11 candidates (including chairmen) in female are winning. In this election in different category result like (UR-12, OBC-14 and SC-2) candidates. There

are 17 victorious in independent members and 11 are associated with political parties. Same as 25 wards in Nawabganj were 11 winning candidates (including chairmen) in men and 12 candidates in female are winning. In this election in different category like UR-13, OBC-11 and 2 candidates in SC communities. There are 22 victorious in independent member and 04 are in different political parties. In Karnailganj there are 25 wards were 16 winning candidates in men and 10 candidates (including chairmen) in female are winning. In this election in different category like UR-03, OBC-21 and 2 candidates are in SC communities. There are 19 victorious in independent members and 07 are associate with political parties. In previous data winning males are 44 both and females 33, category wise UR-37, OBC-46 and SC-06. Total independent members are 61 and party associated winners are 19 in different parties.

Table- 4 Municipal Council –Gonda, Municipal Council Temporal Change Data (In %) Year-2012, 2017 & 2023

Sr. No.	Variable	Gonda				
		Year 2012	Year 2017	Temporal Change	Year 2023	Temporal Change
1	Male	17	15	-11.76	17	13.33
2	Female	11	13	-18.18	11	-15.38
3	SC	02	02	00	02	00
4	OBC	13	11	15.38	14	27.27
5	General	13	15	-15.38	12	-20
6	Party Member	04	11	-175	08	-27.27
7	Independent Member	24	17	29.16	20	17.64

Source- Table number 1.0, 2.0 & 3.0

According to Table No. 4.0, the temporary change in the number of candidates under Municipal council Gonda of Gonda district in years 2012, 2017 and 2023 has been presented in percentage as follows – While a change of -11.76 present was registered among men between the year 2012 to 2017, the rate of

change in the year 2023 was 13.33%. Similarly, a change of -18.118% was registered among women between the year 2012 to 2017, further, the rate of temporary change in the year 2023 remained negative -15.38%. No change was seen in the candidates under Scheduled Caste in the years 2012, 2017 and 2023. There was a positive increase of 15.38 present in the candidates of backward caste in the election years i.e. from 2012 to 2017, similarly the growth rate was up to 27.27 present in the year 2023. The temporary change in the candidates of general category was negative in the election years where it was -15.38 present from 2012 to 17 and -20% by 2023. A radical change was recorded in the party members which is as follows, the negative rate was -175% from 2012 to 2017 and it decreased to -27.27 present in 2023. The temporary change rate in the independent members was positive in the election years which was 29.16% from 2012 to 2017 and 17.64% in 2023.

Table-5.Municipal Council –Nawabganj, Municipal Council Temporal Change Data (In %) Year-2012, 2017 & 2023

Sr. No.	Variable	Nawabganj				
		Year 2012	Year 2017	Temporal Change	Year 2023	Temporal Change
1	Male	13	17	30.77	11	-35.29
2	Female	13	09	-30.77	12	33.33
3	SC	02	02	00	02	00
4	OBC	08	10	25	11	10
5	General	16	14	-12.5	13	-7.14
6	Party Member	00	05	>500	04	-20
7	Independent Member	26	21	-19.23	22	4.76

Source- Table number 1.0, 2.0 & 3.0

According to the table no. 5, the temporary change in the number of candidates under Municipal council Nawabganj of Gonda district in the years 2012, 2017 and 2023 has been presented in percentage

as follows – A change of 30.77% was registered among men between the year 2012 to 2017, the rate of temporary change in the year 2023 was -35.29% (negative behaviour in candidate registration). Similarly, a change of -30.77% was registered among women between the year 2012 to 2017, further, the rate of temporary change in the year 2023 remained 33.33%. No change was seen in the candidates under Scheduled Caste in the years 2012, 2017 and 2023. There was a positive increase of 25% in the candidates of backward caste in the election years i.e. from 2012 to 2017, similarly the growth rate was up to 10% in the year 2023. The temporary change in the candidates of general category was negative in the election years where it was -12.5% from 2012 to 17 and -7.14% by 2023. A radical change was recorded in the party members which is as follows, the negative rate was less in 500% from 2012 to 2017 and it decreased to -20% in 2023. The temporary change rate in the independent members was decline in the election years which was -19.23% from 2012 to 2017 and 4.76%(positive) in 2023

Table-6 Municipal Council –Karnailganj, Municipal Council Temporal Change Data (In %) Year-2012, 2017 & 2023

Sr. No.	Variable	Karnailganj				
		Year 2012	Year 2017	Temporal Change	Year 2023	Temporal Change
1	Male	15	16	6.66	16	050
2	Female	11	10	-9.09	10	00
3	SC	01	01	00	02	100
4	OBC	21	21	00	21	00
5	General	04	04	00	03	-25
6	Party Member	00	02	>200	07	250
7	Independent Member	26	24	-7.69	19	-20.83

Source- Table number 1, 2 & 3

According to Table No. 6.0, the temporary change in the number of candidates under Municipal council Karnailganj of Gonda district in the years 2012, 2017 and 2023 has been presented in percentage as follows – While a change of 6.66 percent was registered among men between the year 2012 to 2017, the rate of temporary change in the year 2023 was constant. Similarly, a change of -9.09% was registered among women between the year 2012 to 2017, further, the rate of temporary change in the year 2023 remained be constant. No change was seen in the candidates under Scheduled Caste in the years 2012, 2017 and it will be increased by 100% in year of 2023. There was no change in the candidates of backward caste in the election years i.e. from 2012 to 2017, similarly the growth rate was constant in the year 2023. The temporary change in the candidates of general category was neutral in the election years 2012 to 2017 and -25% negative responses in year 2023. A radical change was recorded in the party members who is as follows, the negative rate was -200% from 2012 to 2017 and it increase to 250% present in 2023. The temporary change rate in the independent members was negative in the election year which was -7.69% from 2012 to 2017 and -20.83% in 2023.

Conclusion-

Above data present, municipal council election in successive years (2012, 2017 and 2023). In changing pattern of election candidate behaviour in different category. The following data presenting changes and developments in electoral geography not only in Gonda district but also the context of Uttar Pradesh. The review of this field of different disciplines in social studies. The electoral geography identifies spatial patterns of election candidates, voting and voters so, it's defined the particular pattern emerged in this region. In this research three Nagar Palika Parishad in Gonda district are following-Gonda, Nawabganj and Karnailganj all these area, behaviour of election candidates' registration in different manner only in Scheduled Caste candidates shows no changing patten in election years but participation of these category is negligible. Major political parties, glory faces are not progressive. In other hand independent parties, representation is more significant than other. Men and Women (General, OBC, SC) are in flexible participation. In the nutshell of we can say that in different years, in the above municipal council, due to human and geographical reasons, there is a difference in the percentage of women, men, other backward classes, general candidates, party and independent members.

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